

MAIN PROBLEMS CAN BE FOUND WHILE TRANSLATING LITERARY TEXTS

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ABSTRACT

Proper name translation is one of the most challenging challenges that might arise when translating a literary text. This is because of two factors. To begin with, philosophers of language disagree on whether proper names are meaningful or not. There are also the offered translation theories that are inconsistent. In this essay, we shall examine the significance of proper name translations in English literature.

Keywords: *Culture, proper names, literary texts, linguoculture.*

ANNOTATSIYA

Atoqli ot (ismlar) tarjimasi - badiiy matnni tarjima qilishda yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan eng qiyin muammolardan biri. Buning sababi ikki omil hisoblanadi. Birinchisi, til foydalanuvchilarining o'ziga xo'surf-odatlar atoqli otlar tarjimasi jarayonida turli qaramaqarshiliklarga sabab bo'ladi. Ikkinchidan, taklif qilinayotgan bir-biriga zid bo'lgan tarjima nazariyalari ham mavjud. Ushbu inshoda biz ingliz adabiy adabiyotida tegishli atoqli nom tarjimalarining ahamiyatini hamda yuzaga kelyotgan muammolarini ko'rib chiqamiz.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Перевод имени собственного – одна из самых сложных задач, которые могут возникнуть при переводе художественного текста. Это связано с двумя факторами. Начнем с того, что философы языка расходятся во мнениях

относительно того, значимы имена собственные или нет. Существуют также предлагаемые теории перевода, которые противоречивы. В этом эссе мы рассмотрим значение переводов имен собственных в английской литературной литературе.

INTRODUCTION. The interpretation of proper names is one of the most difficult challenges in literary translation. This complication derives from two issues: the lack of a specific theory about name translation and the current trend force. The ambiguity over what to do stems from differing perspectives on the meaning of proper names. It may appear that we are not dealing with a significant issue; but, it becomes more complicated when the names in a literary work have a crucial meaning inside that work. In this situation, the translator has several possibilities; in certain cases, choosing one is practically impossible. The next article will address this issue: the appropriate translation of proper names in Uzbek in literary English texts. The translation of proper names in literature is fraught with uncertainty. This is why we will combine existing trends to determine which one is best suited for translating our corpus of samples. The goal is to demonstrate a consistent theory in the translation of proper names is required. To achieve the aforementioned goal, we must first develop a theoretical framework that allows us to understand all of the many patterns in proper name translation. This theoretical framework is divided into two parts: the first deals with the meaning of proper names, and the second with the delimitation of the many translation alternatives. After we've established the theoretical framework, we'll need to deal with a set of proper names.

Proper names are typically classified into four categories. In the literary realm, they can be used to create names for persons, places, objects, and animals. We will concentrate on people's names and examine how distinct literary universes are established based on the invention of specific names that contribute to making that universe more genuine.

The conflict between culture and translation of proper names. Interaction between language and culture, especially foreign language teaching is evident in the process. A person while learning his mother tongue gradually assimilates his national culture, traditions, and customs perceive. But it is different in learning a foreign language perfectly understands the worldly view of the people and other nations. Today, one of the main goals of language teaching is language formation of communicative language skills in the learner and their enrichment of the socio-cultural outlook, and culture the level of opinions expressed in dialogues is to increase. The complex relationship between culture and language. One of the psycholinguistic processes - translation is an important profession enough. The translation is linguistic in conveying the original meaning of information. The goal is to find the appropriate units and use them effectively will do. It interacts with the foreign language culture of our own culture related to attitudes and individual differences and understanding of the world prioritize certain cognitive processes.

Language lexicon as a means of expressing human culture specifically reflected in the different peoples of the world to define cultural conceptual concepts and reveal their essence helps to give. Proper names are important in certain cultures and are of great importance in revealing concepts. Along with cultural dominants, famous nouns are a nation a symbol of enlightenment and spirituality, and humanity itself in society's special place and formation, its direct and inseparable connection with society, also describes the influence of society on human life. Along with cultural dominants, proper names are a nation a symbol of enlightenment and spirituality, and humanity itself in society's special place and formation, its direct and inseparable connection with society, also describes the influence of society on human life. The translation of common nouns from one language to another is somewhat different and is a complex and multifaceted process. The reason is that famous proper names as a carrier of information about the nation's national culture have properties, including that they have a second figurative meaning can be. In addition, the specific semantics of noun

structures determine the complexity of the translation process. The problem of translation of proper nouns is studied with the following aspects is done: first, in terms of their referentiality, secondly, their connection with nominative and connotative aspects, thirdly, in terms of intercultural communication. T.A. Kazakova's separate lexical methods of translation of nouns emphasize. The main function of nouns is individual identification, they perform their task in the translation process along with comparative autonomies that do not depend on the context participants. Common nouns are important because they are translations to be able to reinforce the text being made in different directions has the ability. How to translate them into a foreign language depends on the translator's choice. These are two of the famous proper names bias feature, to them as non-standard language units specify the approach. In such cases, translation from an interpreter There is a need to create special translation methods in the target language will be done. Translation, transcription, transliteration, and semantics a wide range of ways to modify, describe, copy, and interpret is used.

Literature Analysis and Methods. Language and culture also have their functions in society: 1. Cognitive task. This function of linguoculture is manifested in science. Language is a carrier of cultural knowledge. Through language, we become aware of the universe and ourselves. 2. Representative task. Language and culture help people consolidate the results achieved in the course of their spiritual and material activities. It serves to transmit the subject and information to subsequent generations. 3. Semiotic task. In other words, a function of symbols. Based on generally accepted ideas, we can say that language is a system of signs. They also include cultural symbols. 4. The task of communication. Language is not only a means of communication between people but also a carrier of cultural information between them. 5. Axiological function. Evaluation is a function that teaches you to distinguish between what is good and what is bad. 6. Normative function. Moral norms related to customs and traditions. This includes national, religious, and universal values. One of the topical issues is the correct use of linguistic and cultural aspects in translation. We have set a goal to consider the point

of view of this direction in literary translation and how to convey in the correct form words and thoughts related to linguoculture. To form the ability to engage in communication. This principle means increasing the level of readiness of translation personnel for a realistic approach in situations arising in various cross-cultural communications. That is, it is necessary to ensure the correct coverage of the translation text without difficulty in any difficult situation that requires a translator to have rich knowledge in various fields. A principle that requires both the role of a professional informant and the holder of academic social knowledge. Be able to use disparate data. This principle implies the ability to develop the ability to use one's knowledge in various fields, from translator to translator, precisely on the basis of translation. The acquisition of linguistic and cultural knowledge by specialists in the field of translation should be formed through the disciplines of translation theory, and their correct practical use in the process of translating materials of different genres should be a priority. Of great importance in the process of linguistic and cultural analysis is a thorough study of the linguistic units of foreign languages selected for work in the field of translation. In addition, in order to be able to perceive cross-cultural differences, it is also necessary to understand and study the mentality of the people in the language of the original text. Mastering lexical, grammatical, and stylistic techniques on the spot in accordance with the norms of translation improves the quality of translation.

The task of the translator when translating literary texts is to fully convey the author's purpose of the translated language. In fiction, colors are also widely used to denote the names of heroes. Names are given using colors depending on the behavior of the hero. American writer Joel Heller in "Catch 22" has Captain Black (Captain Black). In the Russian translation of this work (translated by A. Kistyakovsky), the translator calls this character Captain gnus, personifying the negative in the work, stemming from dark, evil, ugly, and ugly meanings of black in English. Gnus can reveal the meanings of the sourcetext in

Russian in excess. If the name Black in the original text was taken in this form in translation, then for the Russian-speaking reader it would be considered just a noun expressing the character of the character and having no meaning. Coloring in English would lose its relevance in Russian. Although the author uses such names precisely in order to give additional information and enhance the emotional coloring. That is why the translation of eminent nouns chosen using colors is a serious matter that a translator must fulfill. In Rowling's novel Harry Potter and the Secret Chamber, the phrase salmon-pink is used to indicate the color of clothing when depicting the jacket of one of the characters. We can see the source text and one of the variants of its translation. She was already wearing a Salmon-Pink cocktail dress. An Evening plate of light salmon was already beating on her. with a literal translation into Russian, a very rude and disproportionate phrase would have turned out. Because none of the languages have exactly the same color. Therefore, the phrase denoting color, when translated grammatically turns into another fragment of the sentence

Conclusion. Instead of a conclusion, we can say that the role of linguoculture is invaluable in artistic translation. In general, without linguistic and cultural knowledge and skills, the translator will not be able to achieve results. It's natural. But the main thing we should pay attention to is the training of qualified translation specialists. Because the concept of culture continues to change as society develops. Consequently, the concept of linguoculture will also continue to be updated. It affects fiction as well as other fields. There is fiction that will definitely be in demand and needs translation. Thus, we must support translators, and create conditions for them to acquire both theoretical and practical knowledge in order to provide a worthy replacement for our translation schools in the future.

REFERENCES

1. Воробьев В.В. Лингвокультурология (Теория и методы). – М., 1997. – 313с.
2. Ермолович Д.И. Имена собственные на стыке языков и культур/ Д.И. Ермолович.–М.:Издат. «Р. Валент», 2001// <http://e-repa.ru/files/translation/ermolovich-names-pt1.pdf>
3. Казакова Т.А. Практические основы перевода / Т.А. Казакова. – СПб.: Союз,2001.—320 с
4. Cronin, M. (2000). “History, Translation, Postcolonialism.” In *Changing the Terms: Translating in the Postcolonial Era*, edited by Sherry Simon and Paul St-Pierre, 33–52. Ottawa: University of Ottawa Press. [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)]
5. Davies, E. E. (2003). A Goblin or a Dirty Nose? *The Translator Studies in Intercultural Communication* 9 (1): 65–100. [[Taylor & Francis Online](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)]
6. Dunne, É. 2010. *J. Hillis Miller and the Possibilities of Reading: Literature after Deconstruction*. London: Continuum. [[Google Scholar](#)]
7. Fernandes, L. (2006). “Translation of Names in Children’s Fantasy Literature: Bringing the Young Reader into Play.” *New Voices in Translation Studies* 2: 44–57. Retrieved May 27, 2016 from <http://www.iatis.org/newvoices/issues/2006/fernandes-paper-2006.pdf> [[Google Scholar](#)]
8. . Timko N.V. *Linguocultural aspects of the translation of color designations*. Kursk-20127.Rustamov, I. (2020).